

Personal Naming Patterns and Preferences among Pashto Speech Community

Ghani Rahman, Khalilur Rahman, Azizullah Jan, Nadeem Haidar Bukhari, Mansoor Ahmad, Salma Bibi

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 07, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: March 01, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Naming, Patterns, Preferences, Community, Pashto, Pakistan.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4570253</p>	<p><i>The purpose of the present study was to analyze personal naming practices for old and new generations of Pashto speech community. It specifically focused on the linguistic properties of these names and the diversity in naming practices. The personal names of the old generation were analyzed for traditional names signifying the preferences for those names. While, the modern trends in naming practices were explored and the possible social reasons for the preferences of modern names were analyzed. The study explored the shift from the association of the community with nature and culture towards modern fashionable trends. For this purpose, 35000 names from the voter list of all the 35 districts of the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province of Pakistan were reviewed and analyzed to explore naming practices across generations. Likewise, 32000 names selected from 8 educational boards were taken to ascertain naming practices across younger generation of Pakhtun. Furthermore, a total of 700 respondents in 4 purposively selected districts were interviewed through convenient sampling. The findings shows that naming practices and patters among Pakhtuns are traditionally driven and religiously influenced. It was observed that thenaming practices of older generation are well integrated into Pashto phonological patterns which are being replaced by modern trends having different phonological patterns and their own complex semantic structures. The changing naming practices are mostly attributed to mass media, education, globalization and increasing population. The gender differences in names were easily recognized through sound symbolism and the traditional female role is reflected in naming practices as well. The study is highly significant for analytical, theoretical and cultural perspective. It highlights theconnection between linguistic practices and socio-cultural beliefs and the modern trends in naming practices for Pashto speech community in today's globalized world.</i></p>

Introduction

Name is a linguistic sign/unit having a form and meaning and referential ability or application. The cognitive content of a name is descriptive of its referent while naming a place or person (Ainiala&Östman, 2017). Naming practices are as old as the Homo sapiens themselves. Through naming, human beings recognize each other and other entities in the concrete or abstract environment during their communication. Naming practices are so prevalent that there is no human without a name. These practices and patterns are influenced by multitude of factors like regions, religious beliefs, national background, social status, gender, family history, ethnicity (Lindsay & Dempsey, 2017; Ainiala&Östman, 2017, Al-Zumor, 2009), traditions, values, events, fears and hopes etc. (Rosenhouse, 2002). The intentional choice of name with careful contemplation provides intrinsic information about the name giver's religious, ethnic and socio-cultural background (Alford, 1987) and further confirmed by availing/not availing the chance to change it by name bearer. Naming is not only social and official registration but one of the important components of identity and its recognition by others (Gerhards& Hans, 2009) helping us in tracing the ancestral connections and historical investigation (Mayrand, 2011). The objects, places and persons are named for their identification and categorization. The general term onomastics is used for the study of names either from typological (Ainiala&Östman, 2017) or etymological (Kostanski&Puzey, 2016) perspectives. The social aspects of names and their uses like the perceptions and beliefs of people are studied in socio-onomastics (Ainiala, 2016) under the premise that naming practice cannot be separated from the social structural of the community as an independent process (Bramwell, 2012). This later complexity of naming practice makes it an interdisciplinary field of study taking into account the social, cognitive, interactive and cultural aspects of naming (Ainiala&Östman, 2017). The toponymy studies the place names (Aksholakova, 2014; Ainiala, Saarelma&Sjöblom, 2012) while anthroponymy studies personal names (Dias, 2018; Fargetti, 2018). The personal names of humans are either family names, nick names or person's first given name. These names have semantic value and a greater role in social interaction (Al-Qawasmi& Al-

Haq, 2016) being essential part of languages (with or without a special category for it) based on semantic, syntactic, phonological, morphological or orthographic principles expanding out insight about identifying cultural and social patterns in societies (Al-Zumor, 2009) used as reference devices to accomplish a variety of relevant social, cultural and interactional tasks (Ainiala & Östman, 2017). The present study focuses on the naming practices among Pashto speech community assuming a strong connection between cultural expectations and linguistic choices for naming (Al-Zumor, 2009) and description of diversity and complexity in the naming system (Agyekum, 2006).

Literature Review

The identity represented through language (names) is stronger than other cultural artifacts like food, dress etc. (Wardhaugh, 2006), that is why previous studies have focused on various aspects of naming practices like linguistic (Zuraiq, 1999; Ainiala & Östman, 2017; Anderson, 2007; Tuffour et al., 2020; Sullivan & Kang, 2019), interface perspective of different principles for naming (Pilatova, 2005; Lima, 2017) and socio-cultural aspects (Al-Quran & Al-Azzam, 2014; Aksholakova, 2014). The linguistic aspect has focused on the choice/rejection of names because of the structural characteristics. The names in some societies are even considered as good or bad names because of the syllabic structure of the name ending (MacAulay, Siddiqi & Toivonen, 2018) and they are not randomly selected but to some extent by sound symbolic principles (Kawahara, Noto, & Kumagai, 2018). The phonological patterns in names are recognized to determine gender in non-native names even (Sullivan & Kang, 2019). An extensive literature reviewed on the pattern and practices of personal names in various contexts reveals that social values, culture connotation, ideology and society are important factors in the selection of names (Ainiala & Östman, 2017; Mattfolk, 2017; Alhaug & Saarelma, 2017) along with historical events, romance backgrounds and cultural specific allusions and metaphors (Al-Quran & Al-Azzam, 2014). Sociolinguists study these communicative practices of existing naming patterns in various communities in particular communicative contexts (Rampton & Charalambous, 2019) along with the linguistic variation patterns by different social groups (Banda, 2020). Names are unadulterated expression of cultural identities, ideas, inclinations and preferences (Eslami-Rasekh & Ahmadvand, 2012). The personal names links with linguistic system, cultural contact and social change have been investigated (Bramwell, 2012) and forename (first name) was found out in all societies during a cross-cultural metanalysis of naming practice but surname (family name) was not found out in all societies (Alford, 1987).

Naming Practices in Other Speech Communities

Naming practices transcend the illocutionary act of labeling to highlight social indices (Odebode, 2012). Naming practices in Kuwait take into account social factors and historical events along with precious metals, plants and sea objects names (Yassin, 1978). Similarly, the political ideology of parents are reflected in the baby names in USA (Pappas, 2013), unlike the religious ideology in sub-continent (Jayaraman, 2005) and social, ancestral, nativity ideologies among African tribes (Olatunji et al., 2015). Names in Kurdistan province in Iran mirror love of nature, virtues, land, and the glorious history of those people. The males are named after hunting animals and plants while females are named after non-hunting animals and flowers (Eslami-Rasekh & Ahmadvand, 2012). The transformation in naming practices in Kazakh for the restoration of historical names for national identity grew ethnic self-consciousness (Aksholakova, 2014).

Changes in Names

The naming practices are changing because of the linguistic, social, political, religious and personal reasons (Al-Zumor, 2009). These changes could be about the choices of name influenced by the socio-ethnic changes in particular time (Sabet & Zhang, 2020) especially reflected in shifts in children's names in quality and quantity (Juncal, 2018). The changes are even observed in elders' names. The innovation in naming practices is linked to many factors. It could be because of the nuclearization of the families today (Unser-Schutz, 2017) or the because of the professional needs like celebrities. The innovation in naming practices was favored by younger performers but the celebrities liked their original name and kept the innovation in names to the stage only (Neethling, 2018). The incomes measure and the age of the bride after marriage allowed the brides to keep their premarital family names or hyphenating them (MacEacheron, 2020). There are many interesting examples of the real effect and use of names in people's daily life and activities. In Lithuania, people generally believe that name has a vital role about the future life of a child and it can determine or even change a child's destiny. In some part of the world, people significantly consider names for their future practices like marriage, for example, in Burma, Medlej (2011) reports that the initial of a child name has association with day in which a child is born, some days are considered to be conflicting with each other, so people born on these days cannot marry, for instance one cannot find a *K* companion with *H* spouse. The previous practices of children having grief names showing grief in the family are now being replaced by Christian and Western names (Babane, 2017). The conservative families tend to name their sons after grandparents, while the young fathers tend to have a contrary view of naming children after borrowed characters or even socially unfavorable persons (Al-Quran & Al-Azzam, 2014). Exceptional names make the children eminent, that is why the social norms are avoided in naming practices to lead the children towards the desired personality traits (Bryner, 2010). The naming and renaming practices in diaspora for an individual has not been documented and the detail microhistories are still rare (Abel, Tyson

&Palsson, 2019).The changes in names in Jordan were affected by moderanization, urbanization and short names tendencies (Al-Qawasmi& Al-Haq, 2016).

Methodology

Universe and Population of the Study

This study was carried out in the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province of Pakistan. The total population of the province is 35.53 million with majority Pashto speaking population called Pashtun (Pakhtun). Pashtuns are generally famous for their attachment with cultural values and religious injunctions. Consequently, Pakhtuns are immensely influenced by cultural norms and religious values which are reflected in their daily lives like naming practices. However, in the past few decades, the traditional outlooks and normative practices of Pakhtun have been replaced by modern and exotic lifestyles. This paper attempted to highlight the traditional naming practices and their changing nature across successive generations.

Procedure for Data Collection and Sample Size

This study was carried out while using positivistic method of study in which data were collected from secondary and primary sources. At secondary level, data were collected from voter lists to examine naming practices of older generation (above 18 years of age) while data were taken from secondary school gazettes to ascertain naming practices of older generation (below 17 years of age).In order to include all the 35 districts of the KP province in our study, voter lists of the general election 2018 were obtained in which 1000 names(both male and female names) from each district were selected thus making a total of 35000 names. Likewise, 32000 names (both male and female names) of students from all the 8 educational boards of the province (4000 from each one) were selected for review and analysis. As most of the names were repeated in the voter lists, only those names were analyzed which were not repeated. Furthermore, a total of 700 parents (name givers/fathers) were interviewed in the four purposively selected districts under convenient sampling procedure.The participants' ages were from 25 to 50 years having at least one child at the time of interview. These participants confirmed the preferences of modern naming practices and the possible reasons for the change in naming practices. The researchers from different areas of the province made the collection of the data easier from the target population. The collected data was carefully analyzed and names from the selected lists were categorized into religious, traditional, family and modern names depending upon the nature of the personal name. Similarly, traditional names were also reviewed to identify them in the light of their association with natural objects or phenomena and religious or cultural beliefs likenames after rivers, mountains, flora and fauna, stars and galaxies, objects, colors, days and places besides some names after superstitious beliefs.Likewise, gender based analysis was also performed to explore how names of male and female are associated with a particular category and identified with natural phenomena. Besides, changing pattern and practices of naming and associated factors affecting these practices explored through interviewing the study participants and analyzed through descriptive statistics.

Results

Pashto speech community though dynamic has vital cultural values and expectations and potential to borrow linguistic elements from other languages which are apparently visible in naming practices. These data for naming practices was categorized into four categories. These categories included traditional names, religious names, modern names and family names. The categories were identified on the basis of personal name by which an individual is addressed (in Pashto speech community the person is addressed by personal name, i.e. first name).

Table 1: Categories of Names in Pashto

Category of Names	Male Names	Female Names
Religious Names	25.41%	3.18%
Traditional Names	14.35%	22.41%
Family Names	17.88%	2.18%
Modern Names	5.88%	8.71%

The traditional names are culture specific unlike exotic modern names where sometimes even the semantic significance is ignored. The high percentage of religious names for male are because of the reasons that religious names are derived from the AsmaulHusna (names of Almighty God) and the concept of God in Islam in general and for Pashto speaker in particular is masculine or at least not feminine along with the concept of Prophethood in line with patriarchal hierarchy for power and divine revelation. This patriarchal reflection is evident even in the naming after the names of the companions of the prophet Muhammad (PBUH) recorded more than the names of the female companions. But unlike religious names, females have traditional names more than males signifying the traditional roles for female in other fields of life as well. Similarly, the males dominate in family names because the female name is still a taboo in Pashto speech community after puberty and the family name is avoided in female naming practices. There is no significant difference in modern male and female name practices. They are called modern names because these names were borrowed from languages through various means. The modern names are more complex than other categories of names because the second name could be either family name, traditional or religious name. The female names are mostly personal names

and if there is second name available (modern trend in female names), it is commonly family name, i.e. father name.

Diversity in Traditional Names in Pashto Speech Community

Names in Pashto speech community have diversity, especially in traditional naming system. The community has traditionally named people after different elements from their surrounding for which there is an apparent shift towards modern names. These names were derived from the names of rivers, mountains, flora and fauna, stars and galaxies, objects, colors, days and places besides some names after superstitious beliefs. The following table contains some examples of these names. The percentages given are out of all categories of names from the selected names.

Table 2: Types of Traditional Names in Pashto Speech Community

Types of names	Male Name	Female Name	Frequency
Names of mountains	Illum Khan	IllumNaz	0.32%
	FalakSer	Shandalai	
Names of colors	Tor Gul	Ziarraqa	0.8%
	Sabz Ali		
	Speen Khan		
Names of objects	Zard Ali		2.56%
	Katoray	Shama	
	Jaam	KhaesMahal	
	Patang	Deeva Begum	
	Zaray	TajMahal	
	Kachkol	Qalam Begum	
Names of days	Payee	Pashmeena	0.64%
	ZyaratGul		
	Itbar Khan		
Names of rivers	Jumma Khan		0.48%
	Abasin		
	Samandar		
Names of stars	Darya Khan		1.6%
	Storay	Spoogmay	
	Shams	Zohra	
	Zamin	Zamina	
	Aftab	QamarGula	
	Qamar		
Names of plants and tress	Jowkay	GulSanga	3.04%
	Chinargul	Nargis	
	Shamake	Gulaba	
	Marchake	Yasmeen	
	InzarGul	Sangooray	
	Sanobar	Kashmala	
	Gulab	Mamanra	
	GuleSadbar	Zeeton	
Names with negative connotation	Kheeran	Hewana	0.80%
	Kameen	Kameena	
	Khachan		
Names of places	Kabalay	Kashmirai	2.08%
	Shamozay	Shamozai	
	Khoshab	Badakhshan	
	Ashnagaray		
Names of gemstones	Chalyaar Khan		1.44%
	Ghamay	Zamarood	
	Yaqoot	Yaqoot	
	Marjan	Marjan	
	Feroz	Feroza	
	Zarqoon	nagina	
	Zabarjad	Jawahira	
Names of birds	Lal		
	Kargha	Kharo	
	Tooti	Kawtara	
	Sharmakahy	Balbala	

	Manzaray	Elai	2.24%
	Totakay	Totakai	
	Tawas	Andaleeb	
Names for special purpose		Balanishta	
		Noreena	
		Basnisa	0.64%
		Noreenishta	

Linguistic Considerations in Naming in Pashto

Pashto names are combination of Pashto consonants and vowels in line with possible phonological patterns in the language (Rahman, 2009; Khan&Bukhari, 2012). In Pashto nouns, the last syllable is stressed which is reflected in naming practices as well. Most of the personal names have stress on the last syllable of the word. The older tradition was the practice of integrating borrowed names into the phonological structure of Pashto. That is why names like *Bkhthwas* pronounced like *Bakh* without the sound /t/ at the end. Similarly other religious names like *Faathma* (name of the daughter of the Prophet Muhammad) was pronounced *Fath maal* like other Pashto traditional names where the last syllable was stressed unlike the name in Arabic from where the name was borrowed. Furthermore, the femininity in Pashto names is reflected in the vowel ending in names and many Pashto female names are derived from male names by adding a vowel sound at the end. For example, the female names *Khalda*, *Famida* and *Rashida* are derived from *Khalid*, *Famid* and *Rashid* respectively. The female names on the other hand do not derive male names, for example, the female name *Rashda* does not make *Rashd* as a male name. The vocative case is used with proper name for addressing someone by name in Pashto by adding vowel at the end of name, for example, *Khalid* is addressed *Kha lida* which is a male name has different vowel quality (/ə/sound at the end) and stress pattern (penultimate syllable is stressed) than female name *Khali de* (having /e/ sound and stress on the last syllable). But if the female name ends on a consonant sound, the vowel /o/ is used instead of /e/, for example *Mumlikato*. The vowel /ə/ comes at the end of both male and female names representing vocative case, while, the vowels /e/ comes after female names and the vowel /o/ for vocative case in female names. The data shows that Pashto speakers had enough clues for recognition of names for different genders. The femininity in female name is mostly represented through vowel sounds and masculinity with consonant sound linking the higher sonority of vowel (sweetness of voice or beauty in names) with female names than with less sonority of consonants (roughness of voice) in the light of obstruction for speech sounds. This is especially true in the case of final sound of names. Most of the male names end with consonant sounds while those of female names with vowel sound. The female names having consonant at the end are borrowed modern names, for example, *Mehek*, *Noreen*, *Maheen* etc. and some names having consonant at the end are used for both gender like *Shamim*, *Sharafat* and *Kawsar*. The Pashto names do not start or end with retroflex plosives /t/ and /d/, retroflex flap /ɽ/, retroflex nasal /ŋ/ and velar nasal /ŋ/.

Naming Preferences in Pashto Speech Community

The preferences of prevalent naming practices were confirmed from the interviews conducted in a systematic manner from 5000 participants from all districts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. These participants were all name givers (parents). The preferences highlight the change from the traditional and religious names to modern names.

Table 3: Naming Preferences in Pashto Speech Community

Category of Names	Male naming Preferences	Female naming Preferences
Modern Names	33%	67%
Religious Names	39%	13%
Family Names	23%	15%
Traditional Names	5%	5%

In modern names, the personal name is a modern name, while the second name could be a family name or religious name. The practice and preference of religious names were almost the same, while there was evident decline in the preference of traditional names, so, affecting their practices too, which are one of the reasons that there is an apparent change in the names in voter lists (elder people's names) and school records (younger ones names). The practices commonly reflect the past affiliation of the community while the preferences reflect the naming practices today and the practices in near future. The traditional names practices have been dissolved in other categories and there is either increase or retention of the preferences for these categories. The data show that Pashto speech community though having strong religious and cultural affiliations prefer modern names for various reasons. The modern names are compound names where the first part is a modern name while the second

part of the name is either family name or religious name. The modern trend of father's name with a female personal name has emerged as a fashion. The female names are mostly mononyms while male names are polynoms because of avoiding family name with female personal names observing the old tradition of female name as a taboo (Khan, 2008). Because of lack of religious names for female, i.e. most of the Holy figures either real human beings or spirits like angels are considered male in Pashto speech community reflected in the names of male here.

Reasons for Change in Naming Practices

The naming practices of traditional names are being replaced rapidly by modern trends. These trends are so attractive that even the linguistic considerations for naming in Pashto are ignored. For example, the practice of stressing the last syllable in old female names in Pashto like *Khlali 'da*, *Fath 'maetc.* is being replaced by stressing other syllables of the words like in the names *Shan 'dana*, *Ja 'varia* where the penultimate syllable is stressed unlike the old tradition of stressing the last syllable. The phonological integration of names is being ignored and we have exotic names without any phonological integration in Pashto. That is why the older names like *Noreena* and *Sabina* are being replaced by *Noreen* and *Sabin* and even the vocative cases are out of use for these names as the modern trends are exotic to Pashto language. The trend is also reflected in names for both male and female. These trends are because of the role of media, education, globalization and increasing population as identified in the data.

Table 4: Respondents' views about reasons for changes in naming practices

Reasons for Change	Frequency
Media	40%
Education	29%
Globalization	25%
Increasing Population	6%

The role of media was claimed to be the greatest cause of change of names. People name their kids after the popular characters in media. The increasing educational ratio was also claimed to be another greater cause of this change in naming practice. Learning other languages and literatures allow the possibility of borrowing names into Pashto. The widespread migration/immigration for jobs and other purposes for Pashto speech community were also claimed to allow them to select names from other communities. The increasing population was the least claimed reason for the change in naming practice.

Discussion

The findings of the study show the vital cultural values and expectations of the community reflected in their naming practices. The data from two different sources showed the older and modern trends of naming practices. The names of old generation were either religious names, traditional names, family names or modern names, where the traditional names was winning the race followed by religious names. While naming their children in the past, the parents/name givers imagined themselves through the prism of their culture, language, religion and ethnicity (Gallop, 2018). Pashto names of older generation were in line with possible phonological patterns in the language (Rahman, 2009; Khan & Bukhari 2012) and the linguistic taboos in the language (Khan, 2008) integrating borrowed names into the phonological structure of Pashto. The femininity in Pashto was reflected in naming practices in the language. The names for different genders were easily recognized from the available phonological clues (Sullivan & Kang, 2019) linking the more sonorant sounds with femininity and less sonorant ones with masculinity, particularly, the last sounds in names. The most sonorant sounds (like vowels and other sonorant sounds) were found more in female names signifying their fragility while males' physical roughness was reflected through less sonorant sounds in their names. The female names had final open syllables while the male names had close syllables in traditional names (Sullivan & Kang, 2019) which are being replaced by borrowed modern names having different phonological patterns and sometimes even the some names are used for both male and female. The unique particularities of form of personal names (Aksholakova, 2014) in Pashto are being replaced by unique particularities of form from other languages having their own complex semantic structures. The linguistic patterns were exploited more in older names in and the female names were derived from male names through suffixation, for example *Khalida* from *Khalid* and *Shahida* from *Shahid*. Similarly, the harmony in persona names of siblings (either all brothers or all sisters) is created by rhyming the last part of the name showing familial affiliation, for example, the names of the brothers like *Talimand*, *Aqalmand* and *Bahramand* were rhymed and the names of the sisters like *Khalida*, *Shahida* and *Rawida* were rhymed. The last sounds were especially prominent, for example, Pashto female names were derived from male names by adding

a vowel sound at the end making a female name of male name suggesting that the only difference between the names of these genders is reflected in the last added vowel sound in female's name and lacking in a male's name. The female names on the other hand did not derive from male names. The recognition of different names for different genders was so important that vowels with different qualities were used or different stress patterns were used in these names. These practices were so prevalent in the past that even the transgender adopted either a male or a female name (Rahman, Rahman & Shahabullah, 2020).

The naming practices in Pashto speech community is sometimes different from the use of these names for addressing people. It is a common practice that the most common names like *Khan* and *Malak* etc. are used with personal names as a necessary part to show the social position of elite families in Pashto speech community (Davies & Harré, 2001) and if they are used with names of people from the lower or middle class, they are commonly addressed by their personal names. There were no matronymic practices found here but there were enough instances of patronymic surnames practices. There was a common practice of ethonyms (both endonyms and exonyms) in Pashto speech community because of ancestors' occupation and cast. The family names though were frequent but less than the traditional and religious names and more than modern names in the names of older generation. The naming pattern in Pashto speech community reflected their social aspects of life. The factor of belief in particular religious sect and ethnic affiliation or patronymic lineage determined the naming practices replacing the traditional names of older generations who were named after days and objects (Olatunji et al., 2015). The practice of religious names has been persistent over the years as the old and new generation names have enough frequency of religious names. The patriarchal structure of power in Pashto society was reflected in naming practices in religious names and most of the religious names were masculine in nature like names after Asmaul Husna (names of Almighty God), names of Prophets and other religious figures. This patriarchal reflection was evident even in the naming after the names of the companions of the prophet Muhammad (PBUH) recorded more than the names of the female companions. Similarly, the family names are still in use with almost the same frequency. The males dominate in family names because the female name is still a taboo in Pashto speech community (Khan, 2008) and the family names is avoided in female naming practices to hide the family lineage. But unlike religious names, the greater frequency of traditional names for female signify the traditional roles for female in other fields of life as well. The diversity in traditional names for older generation showed the attachment of the community with their surrounding environment having names after rivers, mountains, flora and fauna, stars and galaxies, objects, colors, days and places besides some names after superstitious beliefs. The traditional names are being replaced by modern names for new generation. The role of media was claimed to be the greatest cause of change of names. People name their kids after the popular characters in media. The increasing educational ratio was also claimed to be another greater cause of this change in naming practice. Learning other languages and literatures allow the possibility of borrowing names into Pashto. The widespread migration/immigration for jobs and other purposes for Pashto speech community were also claimed to allow them to select names from other communities. The increasing population was the least claimed reason for the change in naming practice. There is always a link between social changes and the naming practice (Sabet & Zhang, 2020) that is why traditional names in Pashto are being replaced by various typical fashionable trends. The modern names are derived through various means from other sources and integrated into Pashto naming practices. The modern names are more complex than other categories of names because the second name could be either a family name, a traditional name or a religious name. The female names are mostly personal names and if there is second name available (modern trend in female names), it is commonly a family name, i.e. the father's name. Selecting shorter names instead of longer ones is one such another modern trend (Ainiyala & Östman, 2017). The changes like political, social and linguistic influence naming practices and the previous association with nature and culture reflected in names is now changing in favor of these fashionable trends (Al-Zumor, 2009). These fashionable trends are so exotic in nature to Pashto culture and language that sometimes even the semantic significance of the name is ignored and we have names without clear signification.

Conclusion

The study analyzed and compared personal naming practices among Pashto speech community of two generations. The linguistic patterns for names of the older generations were analyzed where sound symbolism and structural considerations were taken into account by comparing them with naming preferences for new generation. The findings showed that the vital cultural values and expectations were reflected in the naming practices of older generation which are being replaced by modern trends of naming practices for new generation. While naming their children in the past, the parents/name givers imagined themselves through the prism of their culture, language, religion and ethnicity in line with possible phonological patterns in the language and integrated borrowed names into the phonological structure of Pashto. The class difference was even reflected in the phonological structures of personal names and patronymic surname practices. The names for male and female Pashto speakers were easily recognized from the available phonological clues which are being replaced by borrowed modern names having different phonological patterns and their own complex semantic structures. There was a common practice of ethonymy because of ancestors' occupation and cast. The practices of religious

names and family names have been persistent over the years while traditional names are being replaced by modern names signifying the influence from other languages and cultures because of the role of media, education, globalization and increasing population have introduced typical fashionable trends in naming along other social changes. The frequency of traditional names for female in older generation signified their traditional social role which are being replaced by complex modern shorter names, sometimes accompanied by other part from religious or family name. The previous association with nature and Pashto culture is being replaced in favor of exotic fashionable trends and sometimes even ignoring the semantic significance at the cost of other considerations.

Limitations and Recommendations

The present study was delimited to personal names' practices of Pashto speech community in Khyber Pakhtoonkhwa province of Pakistan. The data for naming practices of old generation was selected through voter lists only. The study did not include the sample from other areas of the country and did not include names from other sources. Similarly, the naming practices for new generation were only selected from secondary schools' gazette books ignoring other sources of names. The data for the perceptions of possible causes of change in naming practices for the two generations was only collected from seven hundred parents only. The study suggests in-depth study of naming practices for the community taking into account all other linguistic, social and psychological aspects not covered in the present study. The future studies could investigate the influences of different languages, cultures and brands on personal naming practices for Pashto speakers.

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Author Information

Ghani Rahman

Assistant Professor, English Department, Hazara University, Mansehra, Pakistan

Khalilur Rahman

Assistant Professor, Sociology Department, Hazara University, Mansehra, Pakistan

Azizullah Jan

Ph. D in Sociology, University of Peshawar, Pakistan

Nadeem Haidar Bukhari

Professor of English, University of Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Muzaffarabad, Pakistan

Mansoor Ahmad

Lecturer Sociology, Kohat university of Sciences and Technology, Pakistan

Salma Bibi

Phd Scholar of Social Work, University of Peshawar, Pakistan
